

Supplementary Material for
*F-LoRA-QA: Finetuning LLaMA Models with
Low-Rank Adaptation for French Botanical
Question Generation and Answering*
(RANLP 2025)

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*“F-LoRA-QA: Finetuning LLaMA Models with Low-Rank Adaptation for
French Botanical Question Generation and Answering”*,
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1 Prompt for Botanical Text Segmentation

The following prompt was used to segment long botanical descriptions into semantically coherent chunks suitable for QA generation:

Task :

Divide the French botanical description below into meaningful
chunks, ensuring each chunk is between 300 to 1000
characters long.

KEEP the botanical text in French as it is. Maintain the
context and logical continuity in each chunk. Separate each
chunk with \n<SEPARATOR>\n (without quotes). Do NOT
provide any other formatting or list; just the chunks
separated by <SEPARATOR>.

```
Here's the description:
```

```
{description}
```

2 Prompt for Question Generation

Listing 1: Prompt for QA pair generation

```
Below is an instruction (in French) that describes a task,  
paired with a context (in French). Write a response (in  
French) that appropriately completes the request.
```

```
### Context:  
{context}
```

```
### Response (All possible questions to ask the context):  
{question}
```

3 Prompt for QA Pair Generation

Listing 2: Prompt for QA pair generation

```
Task: You are an expert in botany and natural language  
processing. Your task is to read the following French  
morphological description of a plant and generate all  
possible question-answer pairs in French based on the  
information provided. Questions should be diverse and can  
include specific, broad, comparative, and contextual  
questions. Focus on creating pairs that enhance  
understanding of the plant's features.
```

```
Instructions:
```

- Questions: Ensure the questions are clear, precise, and directly relevant to the text. Include questions about:
 - * General features (e.g., what are the organs and descriptors mentioned, overall characteristics)
 - * Specific details (e.g., dimensions, shapes, textures)
 - * Relationships or structures (e.g., connections between parts)
 - * Missing or unknown elements (e.g., "Are the fruits described?")
 - * The question and answer pairs should be in French!

- Answers: The answers must be directly extractable from the text and complete sentences where possible.

Include ALL possible pairs of questions and answers in a JSON response with the following structure:

```
{"questions": ["..."], "answers": ["..."]}
```

Plant description:

```
{description}
```